

EUPHEMISMS IN POLITENESS PRINCIPLE

Rabiyeva M.G‘

Doctor of philosophy in philology

Davronova G.I

Bukhara State University Master’s degree student

ABSTRACT

Euphemism is a kind of effective language form used in communication, which aimed to produce reasonable communicative effect. This article provides an information about euphemism and scholar’s opinion about it. In addition, the relation between euphemisms and politeness principles is explored.

Key words: *euphemisms, politeness, taboo, Generosity maxim, the Approbation maxim, the Modesty maxim, the Agreement maxim, the Sympathy maxim.*

Humans are born with the need to communicate with other people. In this case, language as the main means of human communication responds to all changes in society. Of course, human society has had its own moral standards since its inception. Among such standards, communicational behavior is considered the central issue. While speaking about the characteristic aspects of communication behavior, representatives of a certain nationality should definitely use euphemisms.

Euphemisms are derived from Greek, means soft expression, which are used in order to make the conversation more polite and words that appear as synonyms for words and phrases that seem awkward, inappropriate, or rude to the speaker. (Xianhua Meng,2016) For instance, we can use “pass away” instead of “die” or “between jobs” instead of without job. The use of euphemisms in language is determined by the culture in which it exists. According to Rawson euphemisms has a significant role to influence people’s social life by turning taboo and sensitive topics into more polite manner so as to avoid offensive feelings. Such topics are mostly related to death, pregnancy, work, aging, body and sexual relationship. In order to solve this dilemma, linguistic substitution strategy is the rejoice of speakers as in using ‘restroom’ instead of ‘urinate’ (Rasha A. Saeed Alsabbah, 2021)

In 1880s, the first man who used the term euphemism for the first time in English was the English writer Gorge Blunt. He gave such a definition: Euphemism is a good of favorable interpretation of a bad word. In 1991, Allan Kate Burridge published

Euphemism and Dysphemism, a book that is very useful for scholars who study English euphemism from a pragmatic point of view. Burrige proposed that euphemism is the substitution of an agreeable or inoffensive word or term for one that is indelicate, blasphemous, or taboo. Various types of euphemisms are found in the Bible. (Burbidge, 1991).

As we told above we use euphemisms in order to achieve polite atmosphere in our communication . in this occasion euphemisms are deeply connected with politeness and politeness principles.

Politeness is a cultural phenomenon which is a matter of respectful and considerate behavior toward others. There are different kinds of theories about politeness. (Nicolas Allot,2010)

The linguist Geoffrey Leech propose that politeness in speech is conducted by a politeness principle and six maxims, which are: Tact Maxim, Generosity Maxim, Approbation Maxim, Modesty Maxim, Agreement Maxim, and Sympathy Maxim

Tact Maxim minimizes cost to other, maximizes benefit to other. (Leech, 1983) For example, “I saw two drunken gentlemen in the street ”

We know that the word “gentleman” is not suitable for drunken, because the former is positive and the latter one is negative . the speaker is going to adhere tact maxim and by this way he can give humoristic sense to the hearer.

I am still between jobs, while Nick has already got successful job.

In this sentence the speaker adheres his ideas to generosity maxim. Being between jobs refers to whom doesn't have a job, while his friend is making progress in his work. The speaker is minimizing benefit of himself in the conversation in order to show his respect towards Nick.

Approbation maxims in which the speaker minimizes dispraise of others but maximizes praise of others, for example, people can say “you are giving a false coloring to the facts” or “you are equivocating with the truth “ instead of telling you are lying. Mostly, the aim of euphemisms to give others highly appraisal and to minimize dispraise of others.

Modesty maxim means that speaker do not praise or avoid praising self. Sometimes people tell “according to my humble opinion”, “your humble servant” (Hui He, 2018). By telling they show their modesty psychological cultural accomplishments.

Agreement maxim minimizes disagreement between self and other and maximizes agreement between self and other. In some cases people tend to have disagreement with others, but they want to be polite while expressing their opinion. For example:

A: What's your opinion my new dress?

B: They are excellent but the blue one is a better option.

In this dialogue B seems to agree with A by saying the dress is excellent, however she is following "but" to express her real thought.

Sympathy Maxim maximizes sympathy between self and other that's to say the speaker tries to show respect and care to others. For instance:

(1) Setback Williams had sold his big farm down on Beaverdam, as he was **getting** on in years, and him and Mary Sue had bought a little homestead that butted up against the Smokey National Park. (Chappell, Fred, 1990)

(2) We know that Elizabeth would **pass** away when she was only 15, that Henry, on the right of the group, would become a soldier and die young, and that James would be so maladroit on the throne that he would be forced to abdicate. # The artist could not have known these things, but the clarity and directness of this miniature is a valuable record. (Enid Saunders Candlin, 1990)

This maxim can mostly be used with euphemisms which are associated with death and aging. In the (1) sentence "getting on" is reflecting becoming old in years to give more polite manner. Furthermore, "pass away" in the (2) sentence the author tends to show the sympathy for the dead who died in 15 and her family rather than telling "she would die".

However, Brown and Levinson who centers on the notion person's self-esteems, which is referred as face theory criticize Leech's politeness maxims on the grounds that there are so many that they only serve only to catalogue and reflect the phenomena instead of explaining them. And there is a question of the scope of the politeness theory that what is the importance of politeness in language use? (Nicolas Allot, 2010)

In conclusion euphemism is used in order to get polite and inoffensive circumstance in communication. If we can make good use of the language, our conversation will be successful and people's interpersonal relations will be more harmonious. We tried to explore the effective use of euphemisms in politeness principles in which the speaker attempts to offer convenience to others and himself, simultaneously it makes others feel respected.

References:

1. A.Hidayat, Speech Acts: Force Behind Words English Education: Jurnal Tadris Bahasa Inggris,9,2016
2. Allan Kate Burbidge. (1991). Euphemism and Dysphemism. USA: Oxford University Press.
3. Brown, P. & S.C. Levinson. Politeness: Some Universals in Language Usage. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1987
4. Chappell, Fred. The storytellers: Evanston: Spring 1990. p. 196 (17 pages)
5. Crystal, D. & D. Davy. Investigating English Style. London: Longman, 1969.
6. Enid Saunders Candlin. Showcasing the Fitzwilliam Legacy. THE HOME FORUM, 1990
7. "Euphemism." Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/euphemism>. Accessed 11 May. 2023.
8. Hui He. A Study on the Application of Euphemism From the Perspective of Politeness Principle. Atlantis press, 2018
9. Leech, G. Principles of Pragmatics. London: Longman, 1983
10. Nicolas.A., Key terms in pragmatics. New York, 2010
11. Rabiyeva M. Difficulties of Differentiating Euphemisms and Dysphemisms //Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 5. – С. 127-132.
12. Rabiyeva, M. G. (2022). Dysphemism or Euphemism ?. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(6), 61-65.
13. Rabiyeva M. G., Asadova Z. Methods of Using Lexical and Grammatical Transformations in the Translation of Literary Texts //Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. – 2022. – T. 5. – С. 492-494.
14. Рабиева, М. (2023). Kinodiskurs yaxlitligini ta'minlashda verbalvizual komponentlar va ularning ahamiyati. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 29(29). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8964
15. Xianhua Meng, Pragmatics Function of Euphemism in Communication, International Conference on Contemporary Education, Social Sciences and Humanities (ICCESSH 2016)